

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXVII. Effect of Temperature on Coagulation Constants of Ferric Hydroxide Sol.

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During slow coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol with potassium sulphate, the temperature effect on the constants a , m and n of Bhattacharya's equation

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m}$$

has been studied at four different temperatures. The rise in temperature has been found to cause a decrease in the values of these constants.

The results can be well interpreted on the basis of Freundlich's assumption of kinetic theory of coagulation. Similar results can also be derived from Ghosh and Gangopadhyay's theoretical derivation of the above equation assuming temperature as a variable.

Slow coagulation of the sols with electrolytes has been studied in detail by several workers. A relation between concentration of electrolyte and the corresponding time of coagulation has been proposed by Bhattacharya *et al.*^{1,2}. This equation can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m}$$

where a , m and n are constants. These authors^{3,4} have shown that the equation agrees well with the experimental data available in the literature^{5,7}. The theoretical justification of the above equation has been put forward by Ghosh and Gangopadhyay⁶, who have derived the equation from Reerink's equation⁸, which itself has a theoretical basis. In their derivation they have treated temperature⁸ as a constant factor, but if temperature is allowed to vary, the constants a , m and n obviously will no longer have the same value at all temperatures, as these constants are related to temperature either directly or indirectly. Thus an attempt has been made in this paper to study the effect of temperature on the above constants for dialysed ferric hydroxide sol using potassium sulphate as a coagulating electrolyte.

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7. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 765.
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EXPERIMENTAL

The dialysed ferric hydroxide sol was taken and potassium sulphate solution was used as a coagulating agent. The progress of coagulation was detected by recording the changes in viscosity. For each set of observation, 5 ml of electrolyte of known concentration was added to 10 ml of sol and the viscosity was measured at different intervals. Several sets of observations were taken with different concentrations of coagulating electrolytes, but the concentrations of the electrolyte were so adjusted as to cause only slow coagulation. The whole process was repeated at four different temperatures, viz., 31°, 40°, 45° and 50°. For calculation of the values of the constants a , m and n , the graphical method of Bhattacharya¹⁰ was employed. The values of the constants obtained at different stages of coagulation and temperatures are summarised in the Table I.

TABLE I

Sol conc. = 6.064 g./lit.

Temp.	Stage of coagulation, (viscosity) in milli- poise	a	m	n (min ⁻¹)
31°	7.75	0.00400 <i>N</i>	0.00110 <i>N</i>	0.1640 min ⁻¹
	8.00	0.00409	0.00110	0.01670
	8.25	0.00499	0.00110	0.00670
40	7.25	0.00490	0.00067	0.00430
	7.50	0.00490	0.00067	0.00180
	7.75	0.00490	0.00067	0.00090
45	6.75	0.00483	0.00037	0.00077
	7.00	0.00483	0.00037	0.00051
	7.25	0.00483	0.00037	0.00033
50	6.25	0.00476	0.00033	0.00061
	6.50	0.00476	0.00033	0.00031
	6.75	0.00476	0.00033	0.00018

DISCUSSION

During the study of slow coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol, a decrease in the values of the constants a , m and n has been found to take place with the increase in temperature. The values of ' a ', the critical stability concentration, vary from 0.004990 *N* at 31° to 0.00476 *N* at 50°, showing that the value of maximum stability concentration causing no coagulation, is reached at lower concentration as the temperature rises. The value of m , the concentration of electrolyte above the critical value to cause instantaneous coagulation, has been found to decrease from 0.0011 *N* at 31° to 0.00033 *N* at 50°. From this decrease in the value of m it can be easily inferred that a much smaller quantity of electrolyte is required at higher temperatures to cause instantaneous coagulation. Similarly, the decrease in the value of n with the rise in temperature indicates a greater degree of aggregation taking place at higher temperature.⁵

The results obtained are in good agreement with the conclusions drawn from Freundlich's theory of slow coagulation,¹¹ which assumes that only those particles are coagulated, kinetic energy of which is greater than the critical value. It is thus obvious that the rise in temperature would certainly increase the kinetic energy of the particles which would result the coagulation of sol at a low concentration of coagulating ions. Consequently the values of the constants a , m and n of Bhattacharya's equation will also decrease.

The results are also found consistent with the inferences which can be drawn from Ghosh and Gangopadhyay's theoretical derivation⁹, considering the temperature as a variable during the process.

The equation has been derived from Reerink and Verway and Overbeek's equation by Ghosh and Gangopadhyay⁸. They have considered α , β and γ as constant terms having the values

$$\alpha = \frac{0.85 \times 10^{-6} a \gamma^2}{kT z^2} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{ze\psi_0}{2kT}\right) - 1}{\exp\left(\frac{ze\psi_0}{2kT}\right) + 1} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = (\alpha + k) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where a = particle radius, $k=R/N$, z = valency, e = electronic charge, N = Avogadro number, T = temperature, ψ_0 = surface potential of colloidal particles.

It has been further assumed in their final stage of derivation that a and m are

$$a = a_1 \frac{(\beta - 1)}{\beta} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{m} = K a_1 \beta^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where a = critical stability concentration,

m = concentration above the critical value 'a' to cause instantaneous coagulation,

a_1 = a constant near the coagulating concentration C of Bhattacharya's equation,

K = a constant term in Ghosh's equation⁸.

On rewriting equation (4),

$$a = a_1 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

From equations (1), (2) and (3) it becomes clear that on increasing temperature the values of β decrease. The coagulation concentration of electrolyte C of Bhattacharya's equation also decreases with the rise in temperature, hence the constant a_1 , which is very near the value of C , will decrease. Thus equation(6) shows the decrease in the value of 'a' with the rise of temperature.

Since α_1 , in equation (5) is a fraction and $\beta > 1$ as assumed by Ghosh *et al.*⁶, the value of $(\alpha_1 \beta^{-1} \beta)$ will increase or m will decrease with the rise in temperature.

According to Smoluchowski's equation^{12,13} for rapid coagulation

$$T = \frac{1}{8 \pi D a n_0} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where T is time required at a sufficiently high concentration of an electrolyte when the velocity of coagulation is most rapid and constant and $T=1/n$, as has been assumed by Ghosh and Gangopadhyay⁶, therefore

$$n = 8 \pi D a n_0$$

n is the susceptibility of sol to the electrolytes.

As n , the susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte, is ambiguous in nature and depends on the two variables, D , the diffusion coefficient and n_0 , the number of particles, its variation with temperature can not be clearly predicted. The resultant effect of these two quantities with the rise in temperature will determine the value of n .

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